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Abstract book

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Concurrent Administration of Biological Therapy (Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors and/or Immunotherapy) with Definitive Radiotherapy in Patients with Locally Advanced Inoperable Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer

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Tyrosine kinase inhibitors and immunotherapy according to their mechanism of action and disease control pathways, have contributed to significant improvements in response rates, progression-free survival, overall survival, and quality of life.

The combination of immunotherapy and/or tyrosine kinase inhibitors with competitive definitive radiotherapy in locally advanced inoperable non-small cell lung cancer is hypothesized to lead to greater locoregional and systemic disease control due to the existing abscopal effect, meaning disease remission outside the radiation field, through the mechanism of producing new neoantigens during the radiotherapeutic damage to DNA.

Materials and Methods: Patients with locally advanced non-small cell lung cancer, EGFR mutants undergoing anti-EGFR inhibitor therapy or patients with locally advanced non-small cell lung cancer undergoing maintenance immunotherapy following neoadjuvant chemo-immunotherapy, were planned and underwent on concurrent definitive radiotherapy of the lung, after prior 3D or 4D simulation, EBRT/IFRT or VMAT irradiation techniques, conventional fractionation, TTD=66Gy or TTD=60Gy in 33fx or 30fx, 5 times per week.

Results: In all patients after the implemented definitive radiotherapy with concurrent administration of anti-EGFR inhibitor therapy and/or immunotherapy, radiologically confirmed stable disease presentation was observed, with partial disease regression without detection of new lesions and an acceptable toxicity profile. Adverse effects were of mild severity,

including RT-induced mucositis of mild degree; serious adverse events were not detected.

Conclusion: In the course of systemic therapy with tyrosine kinase inhibitors and/or immunotherapy, the addition of radiotherapy to the entire primary volume of the lung represents a safe treatment option to enhance the rates of locoregional and systemic disease control.

Keywords: radiotherapy, abscopal effect, immunotherapy, tyrosine kinase inhibitors, non-small cell lung cancer

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